

44 - SPONSORS ON FOOTBALL SHIRTS. BRIEF RELEASE

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INTRODUCTION

Football is a national passion and sports uniforms mark the identity of a club. When we think of football, we think of memory, of its history. With regard to football shirts, this sacred mantle that represents a lot for the team and its fans, we see that it is a piece that is linked to the history of a city, a club and much has changed in the last decades. Its shape, the use of its colors and design are changed from time to time, but the love one has for her is unique. Today it is a source of income for clubs that receive value from their sales and more than that, they make a profit from exposing company brands in strategic locations of shirts. A trend that began in the 70's and 80's, first in Europe, and later in Brazil.

FREIRE (2011) reports that Brazilians and football have had a perfect marriage. We are, as part of the sporting chronicle, "The homeland of the soccer shoes".

This article presents a brief report about the history of the relationships between football clubs and their sponsors that compete for spaces in shirts throughout the country. With Resolution 5/82 of the CND (National Council of Sports) everything has changed and the possibility of inserting advertising in soccer shirt has become a reality.

Nowadays a football team is not conceived without at least one sponsor who generates income for this team. Values that exceed the millions of reais per contract that help in the maintenance of the main and base teams beyond the payment of the athletes among other things. This form of sponsorship is one of the ways to work with sports marketing since the largest investments in marketing are in football and most of the teams here in Brazil already have sponsors.

At first only the top of the back of the shirts (above the numbers) was used for the sponsorship, but it was noticed that other spaces in the shirt could be used and we started to have what we call Master sponsorship or the main sponsor and smaller sponsorships that use other parts of the shirt like sleeves and numbers. Thus, it is difficult to imagine a club that survives without sponsors in his shirt at the risk of isolation and perish space in the sport Breton.

THE START OF EVERYTHING

RAFIH (2015) reports that the history of sponsorship in soccer began in 1952 when a brand of drinks invests in ads for clubs across the country. SILVA (2013) says that the first team who tried a trick in the Football Association of his country was the club German club Eintracht Braunschweig who used an unconventional strategy to use a sponsor on his shirt and this happened in 1973. The German Federation banned any type of advertising on shirts, including the sports supplier. Only the team shell was allowed. The club took advantage of wearing a clean shirt (without a shield) to enter with sponsor. The idea was to put as a shield of the shirt the logo of the Jägermeister factory in the shirt with an intention to associate directly with the representative of the company to the club.

Logo da empresa Jägermeister

Equipe dEintracht Braunschweig

SILVA (2013) still mentions that this efficient idea was formalized by Günter Mast, president of Jägermeister at the time and later to become president of the club. Eintracht Braunschweig made one of the higher hirings of the season by bringing German star Paul Breitner from Real Madrid with the money they had already received with four years of partnership and pockets full. The fact is that other European clubs began to glimpse something new that could change the course of things. RAFIH (2015) says that by the end of the 1970s clubs around the world were limited in financial matters. There was no support for the modality to be practiced at high levels.

In 1978 in England, when the Football Association decided to abolish restrictions on commercial contracts involving changes to uniforms, in order for the sponsor's name to be prominent, there were reactions of disbelief when the prudence of the measure in football so attached to its traditions. (PLACAR MAGAZINE nº 627).

SPORTIVE MARKETING AND THE SPONSORSHIP OF SHIRTS IN BRAZIL

Sports Marketing is one of the traditional marketing segments that uses sport as a means of aggregating, strengthening, building and is directly related to successful sporting events. (POIT, 2013).

Still according to POIT (2013, P.59) "It is difficult to specify the exact beginning of sports marketing in Brazil". Sports marketing sees in sports a way of linking a product, a brand to a particular modality. In this way, sports marketing that is a variation of promotional marketing makes an association of the image of the athlete, a club or the team to a particular brand to achieve the goals it proposes. POIT (2013).

Sponsorship, from the Latin *patrocinium*, is an aid, or a protection. The concept can be understood from the point of view of economics or from the moral point of view, depending on the situation. According to the dictionary sponsorship is conceptualized as:

"Act of giving protection, support; help, help; costing part or all of a cultural event, sports, a radio or television program, etc., as a marketing strategy, in exchange for publicity." (Michaelis Dictionary).

Sponsorship of football club shirts is one of the main sources of revenue for Brazilian clubs. Much of the revenue comes from exposure of brands in their uniforms. Our clubs take advantage of every space in their uniform to leverage revenue through their sponsors. Today it is common to see the marks printed on the shirts in various spaces as the sleeves and the

numbers of the shirts beyond the front of the shirt and the back. Generally the club has a Master sponsor and may have smaller sponsors that contribute smaller amounts. It is important that the team has a Marketing industry that properly organizes everything related to sponsors and signed contracts.

Thinking about Brazil, football is gaining prominence in all the media and the expectation that is created around a game moves people and it is practically unimaginable to design a club with ambitions without sponsorship.

The first Brazilian club that started to adopt a brand on its shirt was the Democrat of Sete Lagoas - Minas Gerais, legally adhering to the then novelty. This was only possible from Resolution 05/82 of the National Sports Council (CND), which authorized Brazilian clubs to advertise in the uniforms products, activities or commercial or industrial goods, provided that these advertisements occupied a continuous space of at most, 250 cm² and placed on the back of the shirts, above or below the number. Until then the use of publicity in shirts of clubs was prohibited of the Brazilian soccer.

The novelty, in July of 1982, had in the Democrat of Sete Lagoas, the sponsorship of a company of sports material. The value of Cr \$ 500,000 was paid in uniforms, balls, soccer shoes and sneakers. A few days later, the team from Ceará joined the wave, the then president alvinegro, Danilo Marques, made an agreement with the Cearense Association of Savings Accounts. The contract was 48 months and Ceará would receive 16 million cruzeiros in that period. Converting, something around R \$ 6 thousand per year. The Fortaleza was next for a contract with Engri Engenharia. (PLACAR MAGAZINE n° 635). Journalist Juca Kfourri said at one point that the CND's decision was fundamentally correct because it announced "updates and reinvigorated our professionalism, opening up an important source of income for Brazilian clubs" (PLACAR MAGAZINE, 626).

The Internacional team Porto Alegre used a brand in the shirt in early 1982 for the Mar Del Plata Tournament. As it was forbidden to use shirt advertising here in Brazil, Inter used the exterior in a game against Peñarol. The mark was PEPSI Cola. The use of sponsorships was allowed in international matches.

From these facts, there has been a radical change in the design of sports marketing and in the way of seeing club shirts. If at first they were smooth, carrying only the shield at the front and the number at the back, the shirts undergo a transformation where the designer and styles are increasingly daring and the spaces are contested by the companies.

THE SPONSORS IN TODAY'S DAY SHIRTS

The importance of sponsorship in the life of football clubs in Brazil is undeniable. Therefore, teams need to have an effective marketing department that can win advantageous contracts. As for shirts, what we see is a festival of brands of different types of companies that want media exposure. We have included here shorts that both the front and the back usually contain a sponsoring brand. This increase in advertising space generates fractional revenues, several companies invest less so that their image is disseminated through the uniform of a football club. We found that the brands extrapolated the use of their image and etched them into parts of the previously unused shirts, such as sleeves, low backs, shoulders and numbers.

A survey by the company IBOPE Repucom mapped the forms of advertising used by advertisers during all games of the Brazilian Championship of the series A of 2014 to reveal which were the most effective within the environment of the games. With the data collected an interesting discovery was made. It is already known that sponsoring the front of the uniform is the best option, was already obvious because of the excellent visualization and also because it is the most expensive space for a brand to be inside the game. The most relevant finding is the sleeve, which can be seen in any position that the player is in relation to the TV camera.

Perhaps this explains the companies' interest in investing in sleeves beyond traditional spaces such as the front and the back of the shirt. The table below shows the data on which forms of advertising used by advertisers during a soccer match are the most efficient.

1	200 – 250 seconds	Shirt (front) master
2	150 – 200 seconds	Double sleeve
3	150 – 200 seconds	Top shirt (back)
4	100 – 150 seconds	Single shirt
5	100 – 150 seconds	Shirt (front) Shoulder
6	100 – 150 seconds	Shirt (front) sports equipment
7	1 – 100 seconds	Bottom shirt (back)
8	1 – 100 seconds	Shirt (back) number

Adaptado de <http://www.iboperepucom.com.br/noticias/iboperepucom-mapeia-as-formas-de-publicidade>

With the popularization of sponsorship on the shirts and the data placed here, we realize that it is increasingly common to have shirts with several sponsors, several brands that spread through the shirt. In some cases, a real visual pollution that even decharacterizes the colors of the club. A master sponsor who usually wears the front of the shirt and the back above the number and smaller sponsors who use the other parts of the shirt. Days pass, expenses are higher, it is difficult for a team to sign an agreement that includes only one brand for their shirt. And, of course, the club's revenue depends on that, so there are companies willing to do that.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The football shirt is the sacred mantle of a club and marks the lives of those who wear it and their fans. For a long time, the shirts took only the club's brand and number. But from the 70's everything changed with the appearance of advertising brands and sponsorship became part of the life of clubs and their shirts.

A leading team that wants to remain a benchmark must have a strong sponsor. Showing a brand for a football club is one of the great devices that large companies make to add value to their brand. Football is no longer a nostalgic sport. It's a money-making machine with millionaire figures in its advertising contracts. The sacred mantle (shirt) followed the trend and today they are produced thinking of the spaces dedicated to the sponsors, their designer has changed constantly, not always respecting the colors of the team. Alternative uniforms are created and advertising contracts are getting louder and louder, seeking to meet needs. With the advent of the Internet, social networks and facilitated access to the media, it is necessary to have marketing teams qualified to work in this area. Today, the idea of having a football team without a brand on your shirt is inconceivable, the ticket sales, the sale of sports equipment and contracts with the media, such as TV, do not pay all the debts. After all, we can discuss some points.

Many sponsorships in some cases end up polluting the shirt. Club shirts represent the history of past generations that helped to perpetuate love for him. Not always the use of different colors and the excessive use of marks on the shirt are well accepted. The exclusive sponsor gives more prominence to the company that chooses this. Clubs should better manage their negotiations, not underestimate the weight of their shirt and show that this market space adds value to the company. It is prudent to note that more and more spaces in the uniforms are used for brand exposure, but it is necessary to preserve the essence of the

shirt, the colors, the shield and the mystique that bring pride to the fan that uses it.

Key words: Football, Shirts, Sponsorship.

Images:

¹ Jagermeister company logo available at <http://goldecanelafc.blogspot.com.br/2013/10/saiba-qual-foi-o-primeiro-clube-de.html> access 10/15/2017

² Eintracht Braunschweig team available at <https://2.bp.blogspot.com/-OOgFSFdwbs8/TnioAYJ17GI/AAAAAAAAACak/AJ9VVA8QKDK/s1600/eintracht+braunschweig+1973.jpg> access on 10/15/2017.

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SUMMARY

This article provides a brief history of the relationships between football team shirts and their sponsors. Nowadays, it is difficult to see any football club without at least one sponsor in their shirt, as contracts are increasingly important for these teams. At first there was a ban on the use of advertising on shirts, but that changed. First in Europe and later in Brazil with the Resolution of the National Sports Council 05/82. Brazilian clubs have begun to use advertising in their uniforms and now we see that the shirt has become an important part for many companies that want a space in the media exposing their brand. The exhibition on TV is fundamental and, from there, a possible discussion on the subject: the exaggerated use of the marks that can harm this sacred mantle, for the bearer of the fan that uses it.

Key words: Football, Shirts, Sponsorship.

SOMMAIRE

Cet article donne un bref historique de la relation entre la publicité et les équipes de football. De nos jours, il est difficile de voir un club de football sans au moins un sponsor, car les contrats sont de plus en plus importants pour ces équipes. Au début, il y avait une interdiction de l'utilisation de la publicité sur les chemises, mais cela a changé, d'abord en Europe puis au Brésil avec la résolution 05/82 du Conseil National des Sports. Les clubs brésiliens ont commencé à utiliser la publicité dans leurs uniformes et maintenant nous voyons que la chemise est devenue une partie importante de plusieurs compagnies qui veulent un espace dans les médias exposant leur marque. L'exposition à la télévision est importante, et à partir de là, une discussion possible sur la surutilisation des marques qui peuvent nuire à ce manteau sacré, à la chemise et au ventilateur qui l'utilise.

Mots clés: Football, Chemises, Parrainage.

RESUMEN

Este artículo da una breve historia de las relaciones entre las camisetas de los clubes de fútbol y sus patrocinadores. Actualmente, es difícil ver a cualquier club de fútbol sin al menos un patrocinador en su camiseta, ya que los fondos contratados son cada vez más importantes para esos equipos. En primer lugar, hubo una prohibición del uso de publicidad de camiseta, pero eso estaba cambiando, primero en Europa y luego en Brasil con Deliberación 05/82 del Consejo Nacional de Deportes. Los clubes brasileños comenzaron a usar publicidad en sus uniformes y ahora vemos que la camiseta se ha convertido en una pieza disputada por varias empresas que quieren un espacio en los medios a través de la exposición de su marca. La exposición en la TV es importante y, a partir de ahí, una posible discusión sobre el uso exagerado de las marcas que pueden caracterizar ese manto sagrado, orgullo del fan que lo vio.

Palabras clave: Fútbol, Camisetas, Patrocinio.

RESUMO

O presente artigo faz um breve histórico das relações entre as camisetas dos clubes de futebol e seus patrocinadores. Atualmente é difícil ver algum clube de futebol sem pelo menos um patrocinador em sua camiseta já que as verbas vindas dos contratos são cada vez mais importantes para essas equipes. No início havia uma proibição no uso de publicidade em camisetas, mas isso foi mudando, primeiro na Europa e depois no Brasil com a Deliberação 05/82 do Conselho Nacional de Desportos. Os clubes brasileiros passaram a utilizar a publicidade em seus uniformes e atualmente vemos que a camiseta se tornou uma peça disputada por várias empresas que querem um espaço na mídia através da exposição de sua marca. A exposição na TV é importante e a partir daí uma possível discussão sobre o uso exagerado das marcas que podem descaracterizar esse manto sagrado, orgulho do torcedor que a veste.

Palavras – chave: Futebol, Camisetas, Patrocínio.